

The Significance of Competitive Orientation and Customer Orientation that Affect Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiencies: The case of Bule Hora University, Ethiopia

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Abstract – The purpose of this study aims the Influencing factors that affected of Competitor Orientation and Customer Orientation on Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency, the case of Bule Hora University, The general objective of the study is to investigate the Influencing factors that affected of Competitor Orientation and Customer Orientation on Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency' expressed and latent needs and develop superior solutions for those needs. The research idea stems from study findings that Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation has not only affects the sustainability of Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency the concern directly that has confounding directly and indirectly. On the basis and types of data gathered and the instrument used, quantitative research design to use Exploratory factor analyze and the data analysis were employed for sample size determination valid 361 respondents and as most of the respondent replied to major effect of Competitor orientation, and Customer Orientation of data have been collected from Teachers or Academic staff of Organization, employees of the Organization and customers of Organization. The scales have been purified and validated with the help of Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the results of structure equation modeling (SEM) revealed a significant relationship between which yielded to the significant results to used data of SPSS Version 20 and AMOS 23 to analysis SEM, Standard Regression Weights and model fit value.

Keywords: Competitor Orientation, Customer orientation, Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the mid-20th century, marketing theory has built upon the marketing concept, to developing country that toward an entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency, which has been heavily studied since the mid 1990's (Kumar, Jones, Venkatesan& Leone, 2018) and as a strategic orientation, and organization that possess the market orientation practices are said to be highly responsive to information flowing from external to the Organizational sources, and such as supply chain members, customers and competitors and Concurrently, such responsiveness is aided by an internal capacity of the organization to the readiness to act on market information practice manifested in well-developed social, and cultural inter-functional capabilities, and an Organization is able to produce internal outcomes through new to the Organization innovation, whereas external effects are manifested by new to the market innovation process and practice to create new idea in the organization, (Sandvik N., 2016).

(Kolinsky Jordan J., 2015), as a broad organizational and university philosophy, of market orientation helps shape Organization processes, to be externally that focused, while to driving decision making with market competitor, and industry intelligence, and it has to be heavily studied construct in its entirety, made up of customer orientation or the ability to create value for the customer continuously, for the

achievement of competitor orientation where the seller understands the key strengths, weaknesses, strategies and capabilities of the competition, and inter-functional coordination, of utilization of the companies' resources (Never & salter, 2017).

In addition, much thought has been put into the role market orientation plays in the context of University and the effect it has on Organization performance that including digital business formats (Hair et al, 2017), the University possess specific challenges and unique advantages, as compared to large Organization, in so much as their size, of the limited organizational structure, and the informal modes of operation allow them to be fast, in response to changes related to customers or competitors and yet at the same time, they lack the resources of larger Organization, and are less able to take advantage of volume discounts, expansive supply chain partner networks and financial leveraging tactics, (Leitner& Goldenberg, 2015).

In this paper, we take these differences into account and propose that the broader (Wolff& Petty, 2016) of the managerial orientation-related constructs are insufficiently nuanced tools, particularly in the study of University. Research suggests that subcomponents that make up these constructs (such as market orientation) are likely to have differing effects on an Organization and it follows, the Organization of internal constraints are likely, to shape the effects of its various practices to some degree, of the different market orientation constructs mentioned above , between customer and competitor orientation are outward that can facing in nature, while inter-functional coordination, is an internal construct affecting the internal workings of an Organization and in this current research considers, the role customer and competitor orientations play the market, and industry performance outcomes when mediated by product and process innovation, (Lonial& Crum, 2019).

To address this inquiry, background literature and prior research is explored, followed by the

development of a formal hypothetical model, which explains (Gada Gizachew W., 2021), in the context of to generate research based development of Innovation of new idea generation to develop and expand revenue generate, to satisfy his customer to take a dramatic service, to increase his production efficiency, purified income generation, and to maximize Enterprise by Competitors orientation and Customer Orientation process for the case of growth university, by, Innovation, innovativeness, Creativeness, by production Efficiency to take a risk, Creativeness, customer response and Customer focus, to contribute Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency.

So, in this research that aimed to investigate Factor influencing with the predictive respect to certain indicators to fill those gap and build the role of Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation have on Entrepreneur marketing Efficiency, in public university of Bule Hora, Ethiopia.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyses the extent to which the relationship between Competitor Orientation that effects on Entrepreneur marketing Efficiency.
- To identify the extent to which Customer Orientation relationship that influences on Entrepreneur marketing Efficiency.

3. COMPETITOR ORIENTATION

(Narver & later, 2016), based on Competitors Orientation asserted that competitor orientation is one of the dimensions of Market Orientation, that helps Organization in identifying, and analyzing current, and potential competitors taking into consideration a complete set technology required to satisfying current and potential customer's needs, in this circumstance, surveying the competitors' position that can assist Organization to identify the rising substitutes, the degree with which such substitutes can be the technologies, and the moments through which technology shifts and In

fact, and the position of this information is instrumental to research and development planning since such can be used to determine when to enter the market and how to select the appropriate strategy that will help in improving performance.

4. INNOVATION

(Damanpour et al, 2019), An innovation can take the nature of coming out with new product, new production technology or a new strategy regarding employees that the businesses does not practice formerly opposite that involvement of customers in organizational innovation teams is rapidly becoming more prevalent and it understanding consumer needs, and knowing their purchase behavior is a critical insight for managers involved in innovations during searching and implementation period based on the, (Saemumndsson, 2016), the Consumers are the best judges of the to create innovation; and that influence on the extent to which innovation strategy will influence on Organizational performance.

5. CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

If your business has positive customer satisfaction, then you have customers who are loyal to your organizational brand and these customers will refer new leads to your company it satisfied by each services and it generate more testimonials for your marketing team and you can create customer advocacy programs for these users, and encourage them to advertise on your business activities that behalf and Customer advocacy programs reward customers for referring your business to potential leads and Customers are given incentives to join the program, additionally, they receive gifts or offers in exchange for reviews and testimonials, (Damanpor et, al, 2019).

6. PRODUCTION EFFICIENCIES

It means your coffee and other beverage business is able to produce the highest number of goods, and

the efficiencies of production system that provide, that has using at a least amount of money, and resources and it's when you produce as much as possible without wasting our resources or sacrificing your products quality whilst maximizing your cash, and People often thinks efficiency is similar to productivity but actually, it's not and they may be directly related to each other, but they are completely different things and the Productivity is the measurement of how much you make over a specific period of time, and the production Efficiencies of each product, is well in our accomplish this task, and it's about the quality rather than just the speed of production system to be highly, launched of our work, (Cooper and Dunkelberg, 2016).

7. ENTREPRENEUR MARKETING ORIENTATION EFFICIENCY

(Cunningham& Lischeron, 2017), Entrepreneur Marketing Orientation Efficiency, after explorations by entrepreneurial organizations, in social and economic context, entrepreneurship was proposed to describe the behaviors of entrepreneurs and individual traits and there is a lack of a universally accepted definition of entrepreneurship in most studies, which focused on small samples and did not adopt time-tested analytical methods in the early stage and classified three strategy making modes (the entrepreneurial mode, adaptive mode, and planning mode) and investigated the linkage between decision-making process and strategy formation.

8. INNOVATIVENESS

Innovation can be it refers the creative development of new products, and markets, was firstly proposed by Schumpeter to describe the entrepreneurial functions, based on the, (Kreiser et al., 2016), the innovativeness that refers, to the tendency to the engagements to support new ideas, novelty, experimentation, and creative processes that may result in new products, service, or technological

processes' (Lumpkin N., 2016), and it suggested that there are many different forms of innovation, such as technological innovativeness, product-market innovativeness, and administrative innovativeness additionally, Innovativeness involves the processes and minds of developing new products, services and creating new market and customer needs.

9. RISK TAKING

Risk-taking it has to be refers to the degree to which managers are willing to make large, and risky taking to his own resources commitments and Uncertainty, which occurs in the changing external environment, and internal organization, is a threat to success, and comes with potential risks and it proposed of types of risk-taking that corporation, and entrepreneurs may confront namely business risk-taking, financial Entrepreneurs tend to perceive a business environment more positively and are likely to take risks, (Palich & Bagjey, 2015).

10. CREATIVENESS

Pro-activeness it has to be refers to an opportunity of seeking, forward for looking perspective involving new products or services as ahead of the competition and acting in anticipation of future demand to create change, and shape the environment and it Previous studies proposed two main aspects of pro-activeness actions to recognize the changes, and size of opportunities and another is that a corporation forward for looking mind is essential to entrepreneurs who want to out-perform and beat rivals of Compared to innovativeness and risk-taking, creativeness received less attention from prior researchers (Kreiser et.al, 2019).

11. CUSTOMER ORIENTATION

(Backar and Sinkuilia M., 2019), that proposed that both customer orientations have a learning construct and they needs, and preferences of customers which a customer orientation focuses

primarily on are parts of market information to share highly for customer and other user of the organizations, and other market factors, such as rivals, technology, industry policy, also can influence the success of an organization, and an Organization with an entrepreneurial orientation efficiency it can capacitated upgraded his achievement take risks, actively acknowledge and respond to market opportunities.

12. CUSTOMER RESPONSE

Productive customer response Performance of the indicator the determines the number of customer in order processed per human-hour and must be done is such a way that the time taken for processing is minimal to increase the productivity using competitor and customer Strategies used in customer service automation can bring immediate improvements, in call center automation, internet ordering, contact management automation, and it integrated customer response systems cuts off the need to hire more employees as everything is automated and it can also compute which customers are profitable for the organization and which are not and which are they who can continue to limiting the investments to made by the organization, and always keeps a check on customer response to highly enhanced financial features, (Backar and Sinkula, 2019).

13. CUSTOMER FOCUS

An approach of customer focus centers business decisions around customers that need a Businesses prioritize serving their customers instead of maximizing profits based on how those choices affect customers for the long-term approach fosters trust and loyalty, and it can generate more internal and external revenue generate to upgrade the organization to launch by his own resources in universities and It's a mindset, philosophy, or a strategy to align your business processes with customer's goals and expectations and when you and since your success is dependent on the success

of your customers, it's a winning combination (Miller & Friesrn, 2018).

14. INVESTIGATION GAP

Usually, following revising diverse publications, it has noted that diverse investigations have been completed on the topic of Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation, (Lubbadeh, 2021). The over the many research journal and investigation credentials have the many problems gap in statement of the problem and problem statement to derive time, (Lesener 2019); challenge in the process of University Entrepreneur Orientation Efficiency and unravel to investigate in Organization Research academy has to fill the problem gaps of Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation and University Entrepreneur Orientation Efficiency.

The association to investigation Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation predictor in the worth research parameters of technique logical vacuum of theoretical and empirical gap with citation problem and copy pasts in many research paradigms (Strah & Rupp, 2020); like Investigation research approach quantitative, quantitative and mixed, to research design to Explore build the model, Information analyze and Interpretation based on the output of data (Pereira et. al., 2021). Sampling technique strategy for population category of homogeneity and heterogeneity was face challenge to give good reason for sample size determination for large data sample size fill small sample size in study time, deficit of methodological philosophy gap based on the theory or research approach to analyze and interpreted each problem (Guthier et. al., 2020; Halcomb wt. al., 2018).

It Deficits of Information Source, and Collection Techniques, deficit of data analyze and interpreting ability and finally, defecating factors that affect influencing Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation, Entrepreneur Orientation Efficiency process Exploratory factor analyze (EFA) predictor investigation not fit Thus, investigation of Market orientation practice has put forward to solve these

gaps (Waitangi &Wakaba, 2014). Thus, study will have solved the problem of the performance of Coffee Marketing to rise to fill these gaps (Waitangi, S. Wakaba, 2016).

15. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: AMOS Output Conceptual Framework

Fig -1: AMOS Output Conceptual Framework

16. HYPOTHESES

H1a: There is statistically significant effect association among Competitor Orientation and Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency.

H2a: There is statistically significant influence association among Customer Orientation and Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency.

17. INVESTIGATION TECHNOLOGY AND DESIGN

Based on the research purpose the study, most commonly used the research philosophy of research Paradigms has designed Quantitative and Deductive research approach, the data analyses designed with Exploratory factor analysis (EFA), to be used for the cases of statistical conclusion to collect actionable insights of essential and number provide the better perspective for making and to draw from complex numerical data and analyze to prove by SPSS software to analysis by Exploratory factor

analysis (EFA), to analysis Correlation Matrix of Significant P-Value tested, KMO, Communalities, Average variance Extracted, Rotated Component Matrix, Component rotated space and to test Convergent construct validity and Discriminate Reliability to test Cronbach alpha of Exploratory Factor Analyze for statistical data that attempts to identify the smallest number of hypothetical constructs, that can parsimoniously explain the covariance that observed among a set of measurement model that are directly influenced Indigenous variable in the scores attained by those people on the measurement value of variables that can be described by, (Brown, 2016).

18. TARGET POPULATION AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Data has collected from the organization Staff member, Academic staff, Administrative Employee of Organization and Customer to use in University has respectively for 3700 respondents population, and study is basically targeted with in Organization Ethiopia thus population has to assorted from different category of each stratum has targeted population of this study. In literature, probability sampling is a simplified method where equal opportunity is given to individual from Members of Bule Hora Universities, the population to be chosen (Saunders 2010).

19. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Simple random sample data of population of the University to use sample from Organization Staff, Academic staff, Administrative Employee of Organization and Customer to use in University has an equal chance of assortment of the Organization, that has to be selected and Stratified random sample and Simple random sampling technique: (Yaqub, M, Sahil, F., Shabr, J., and Sohail, M.U., 2022). So, the For Competitor Orientation and Customer participated to collect data for the validation of this study.

Sample Size

The degree of precision desired, objective(s) of research by taking these factors in to consideration, the researcher was employed, According to Universities (2022) six month report, does the Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency to develop research based new design to generate additional revenue to upgrade organization which is found in Organization, in Ethiopia. However, the study purposively selects from University members are taken as participants in this study, Benouahmane, B., Annie, C., & Yaman, I., 2019) as follows:

$$\frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{3700}{1 + 3583(0.05)^2} = 361$$

20. VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Test The research instrument designed in this study – before being distributed to 20 respondents was first tested for the validity and appropriateness of each statement item made in the instrument. For this reason, at this stage, pilot test questionnaires were distributed to 20 respondents, in this case, from Organization Staff, Academic staff, Administrative Employee of the Organization and Customer to use in University that used 3rd generation public university, in Southern Collider of Ethiopia unique University the results of the validity and reliability test of the research instruments in this study obtained that the entire statement items were valid and reliable to be used for the next test.

21. EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSES (EFA) ANALYSIS

Source: Exploratory factor Analyses (EFA) Measurement Model

Fig -2: Exploratory factor Analyses (EFA) Measurement Model

22. CORRELATION MATRIX

Table -1: Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix ^a									
Cor	COR1								
COR1	1.000	.563	.563	.348	.361	.161	.312	.374	.203
COR2	.563	1.000	1.000	.348	.311	.050	.204	.297	.191
COR3	.563	1.000	1.000	.438	.311	.050	.204	.297	.191
CUO1	.348	.348	.438	1.000	.584	.292	.449	.421	.241
CUO2	.361	.311	.311	.584	1.000	.335	.390	.447	.284
CUO3	.161	.050	.050	.292	.335	1.000	.450	.403	.149
EPM1	.312	.204	.204	.449	.390	.450	1.000	.592	.160
EPM2	.374	.297	.297	.421	.447	.403	.592	1.000	.505
EPM3	.203	.191	.191	.241	.284	.149	.160	.505	1.000

a. This matrix is not positive definite.

Source: Correlation Matrix, (2022)

Correlation matrix table that display the correlation coefficients for different variables that depicts correlation between all the possible pairs of value, it is a powerful tools to summarize large data set to identify all visualize pattern in data set, it can be seen at all the variables are positively correlated necessitating the significance arrow 1 diagonal number is more than 0.3 the variables after delated correlation Value of Competitor Orientation.563, Customer Orientation .438, Entrepreneur Market Orientation .584 in the field of correlation coefficient

as justified for the use of Exploratory factor analyzing hypotheses tests to be acceptable and positive significant correlation matrix in this study.

23. CUMULATIVE TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Table -2: Cumulative Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
	1	3.722	41.354	41.354	3.722	41.4	41.354	2.845	31.606
2	1.701	18.904	60.258	1.701	18.90	60.258	2.579	28.652	60.258
3	.925	10.274	70.532						
4	.746	8.291	78.823						
5	.592	6.581	85.404						
6	.515	5.719	91.123						
7	.438	4.870	95.993						
8	.361	4.007	100.000						
9	.016	3.117	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Cumulative Total Variance Explained 2022

The present scree plot output result which corresponded Eigenvalue Eighteen Measurement construct separated only four measurement construct higher than 1.0 measurement construct value has to be returned. An elbow towards a less step observation scree plot and curve of declined value higher than 1.0 eigenvalue of doubt should be arise three factors has to be returned. Based on this reason the scree plot separation has to be accepted.

24. KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST FACTOR ANALYSIS

Table -3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Table3. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.841
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2605.541
	df.	5
	Sig.	.000

Source: SPSS Output 2022

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin, that has to predict the investigation is appropriate the information that calculated, the result is a statistical measure to determine how suited data is for factor analyzed and the test measure sampling adequacy for each variables in the model to measure the proportion of variance, among enablers and as of these information, the test of Bartlett is considerable .841, that is associated as Chi-Square 2605.541 Degree of freedom 5 probabilities is less than 0.05, to the information P- Value result is .000 it shows highly fitted data to the organization.

25. COMMUNALITIES

Table -4: Communalities Measure of Variance Variable

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Competitor Orientation1	1.000	.577
Competitor Orientation 2	1.000	.939
Competitor Orientation 3	1.000	.930
Customer Orientation 1	1.000	.637
Customer Orientation2	1.000	.552
Customer orientation3	1.000	.708
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 1	1.000	.610
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 2	1.000	.597
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 3	1.000	.664
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Communalities Measure of Variance Variable 2022)

The Communalities information investigation observed communality is the squared correlation

with its own ordinary proportion which predict and enabler that is ordinary predicators and in other sense the communality is the square of predicators, whereas greater communalities higher than .50% that highly predicted value of the Communalities of information were Calculated Competitor Orientation Question indicator value .939 to be tasted in the Communalities test.

26. SCREE PLOT

Source: SPSS Output of Scree plot 2022

Fig -3: Scree plot

The present scree plot output result which corresponded eigenvalues Eighteen Measurement construct separated only four measurement construct higher than 1.0 measurement construct value has to be returned. An elbow towards a less step observation scree plot and curve of declined value higher than 1.0 eigenvalue of dobout should be arise three factors has to be returned. Based on this reason the scree plot separation has to be accepted.

27. PLOT MATRIX ROTATED SPACE

Source: Plot Matrix Rotated Space 2022

Fig -4:Plot Matrix Rotated Space

The common situation where numerous variables of rotated matrix that are highly rotated and loaded moderately, in each component three has rotated three times in each components of matrix, and it can sometimes be alleviated by a other rotation of the components after the initial cases and the aim of this additional rotation is to obtain simple structure where the coefficients with in a component are as close to one or zero as possible and the results will be supported.

28. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS OF FACTOR OF LOADING

Table -5: Principal Component Analysis of Factor Loading

	Component		
	1	2	3
Competitor Orientation 1		.683	
Competitor Orientation 2		.965	
Competitor Orientation 3		.965	
Customer Orientation 1			.703
Customer Orientation 2			.685
Customer orientation 3			.705
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 1	.774		
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 2	.737		
Entrep. Marketing Orientation 3	.654		
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.			

Source: Principal Component Analysis of Factor Loading 2022

The rotated component matrix referred to as a loading is the key output of principal component analyze, it contains estimates of both Exogenous and Indigenous variables separated in five Components, the value of all variables with significant separation and to calculate the loading factor based on output value shows $\geq 0.60\%$ the Cronbach alpha value 0.70% and AVE% results has also $\geq .50\%$ estimated and the major rotation oblique are generally best predict, when all prior information has to be highly loaded.

29. CONVERGENT AND COMPOSITE RELIABILITY RESULTS

Table -6: Convergent and Composite Reliability results

Item	Measurement variables	Cronbach Alpha	KMO	Comm unalities	Factor Loading	AVE %
	Customer and Competitor Orientation					
	Competitor Orientation	.805	.877			.553
COM1	Competitor Orientation 1			.577	.683	
COM2	Competitor Orientation 2			.939	.845	
COM3	Competitor Orientation 3			.939	.865	
	Customer Orientation	.747	.841			.529
CUM1	Customer Orientation 1			.577	.703	
CUM2	Customer Orientation 2			.939	.685	
CUM3	Customer orientation 3			.939	.705	
	Entrep. Marketing Orientation	.817	.831			.520
EMO1	Entrep. Marketing Orientation 1			.610	.774	
EMO2	Entrep. Marketing Orientation 2			.597	.737	
EMO3	Entrep. Marketing Orientation 3			.664	.654	

Source: SPSS Output Convergent and Composite Reliability results, 2022

It Construct convergent Validity and Discriminate reliability extracted common factors have factor loading varying from 0.615 to 0.831 which show that they are well above the critical value of 0.70, the construct reliability level assessed based alpha value .724 that it shows, the high measurement instrument reliability level. KMO index are varying 0.877 value result, which are either equal or AVE% Value above 0.50, depicted sufficient and sampling adequacy overall Communalities is more than 0.5

and the result for further reduced of variables in the proposed model to using SPSS v.22 used to Construct Validity and Discriminate Reliability investigation fit this model highly accepted.

30. CONCLUSION

Correlation matrix table that display the correlation coefficients for different variables that depicts correlation between all the possible pairs of value, it is a powerful tools to summarize large data set to identify all visualize pattern in data set, it can be seen at all the variables are positively correlated necessitating the significance arrow 1 diagonal number is more than 0.3 the variables after delated correlation Value of Competitor Orientation.563, Customer Orientation .438, Entrepreneur Market Orientation .584 in the field of correlation coefficient as justified for the use of Exploratory factor analyzing hypotheses tests to be acceptable and positive significant correlation matrix in this study.

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The common situation where numerous variables of rotated matrix that are highly rotated and loaded moderately, in each component three has rotated three times in each components of matrix, and it can sometimes be alleviated by a other rotation of the components after the initial cases and the aim of this additional rotation is to obtain simple structure where the coefficients with in a component are as close to one or zero as possible the result will be supported.

The rotated component matrix referred to as a loading is the key output of principal component analyze, it contains estimates of both Exogenous and Indigenous variables separated in five Components, the value of all variables with significant separation and to calculate the loading factor based on output value shows $\geq 0.60\%$ the Cronbach alpha value 0.70% and AVE% results has also $\geq .50\%$ estimated and the major rotation oblique are generally best predict, when all prior information has to be highly loaded.

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Construct Validity and Discriminate Reliability investigation fit this model highly accepted.

31. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Nonetheless, this study, like all others, has limitations. To begin, because this is a theoretical paper, upcoming research should empirically prove the study's claim. Second, this model is focused on University; future research should verify its validity in, other universities, larger companies, SME's and different sectors.

REFERENCES

- [1] Antonio N. (2015). of risk-taking that corporation and entrepreneurs may confront namely business risk-taking, financial risk-taking, and personal risk-taking. *Journal of business and leadership*, 234-243.
- [2] Backar and Sinkuilla M. (2019). (Kreiser et.al, 2019). *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 234-246.
- [3] Backar and Sinkula. (2019). (Miller & Friesrn, 2018) . *Journal of Multi decipilinary research design*, 245-260.
- [4] Brown. (2016). parsimoniously explain the covariance that observed among a set of measurement model that are directly influenced Indigenous variable. *Journal of business and management*, 456-467.
- [5] Creswell 2003, cited in Isaq. (2019). SEM analyze of to measure structural model to design Regression model of Standard Regression Weights to measure direct and indirect effect, Correlation and hypostasized direct and indirect effect to investigate the research. *International Journal of Business and Social Researc*, 238-270.
- [6] Dr.A. Shaji George, A.S. Hovan George, Dr.T. Baskar, & Digvijay Pandey. (2022). The Transformation of the workspace using Multigigabit Ethernet. *Partners Universal International Research Journal (PUIRJ)*, 01(03), 34-43.
- [7] Cunningham& Lischeron. (2017). the limited organizational structure, and informal modes of operation allow them to be fast, in response to changes related to customers or competitors. *Journal of logistics and Supply Chain management*, 324-340.
- [8] Damanpor et, al. (2019). Customer advocacy programs reward customers for referring your business to potential leads. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 123-140.
- [9] Damanpour et.al. (2019). An innovation can take the nature of coming out with new product, new production technology or a new strategy regarding employees that the businesses does not practice formerly opposite that, involvement of customers in organizational innovation. *Partner Universal international journal*, 342-353.
- [10] Dubihela and Dhurp. (2015). bemerging some universities market Efficiency. *Journal of Business and Management*, 234-250.
- [11] Gada Gizachew W. (2021). the role Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation have on Entrepreneur marketing Efficiency . *lternational journal of multi deciplinary research*, 1-10.
- [12] Hair et al. (2017). he role market orientation plays in the context of University and the effect it has on Organization performance. *Journal of business and Economics*, 453-464.
- [13] Karmani, N. Y. (2020). comfirmatory factor analyses teacher leadership measurement model. *International journal of Academic Research in Business and Social science*, 697-706.
- [14] Kolinsky Jordan J. (2015). a broad organizational philosophy, market orientation helps shape Organization processes to be externally focused, while driving decision-making with market and industry intelligence. *International journal of multideciplinary research*, 456-470.
- [15] Kreiser et.al. (2019). Organization can generate and disseminate market knowledge through the whole organization and functions. *Journal of business and Leadership*, 123-150.
- [16] A.S. Hovan George, A. Shahul Hameed, A. Shaji George, & T. Baskar. (2022). Study on Quantitative Understanding and Knowledge of Farmers in Trichy District. *Partners Universal International Research Journal (PUIRJ)*, 01(02), 5-8.
- [17] Kumar, Jones, Venkatesan& Leone. (2018). marketing theory has built upon the marketing concept, developing toward Entrepreneur Marketing Efficiency. *International Journl of Business and interpriniourship*, 189-201.
- [18] Leitner& Goldenberg. (2015). the limited organizational structure, and informal modes of operation allow them to be fast, in response to changes related to customers or competitors. *Journal of Management and Social Science*, 567-570.
- [19] Lonial& Crum. (2019). the three market orientation constructs mentioned above, two customer and competitor orientation are outward facing in nature, while inter-functional coordination. *Journal of accounting and finance*, 432-450.
- [20] Miller & Friesrn. (2018). implement this strategy in your company, all your business departments work towards the same goal of customer

success. *Journal of business and Economics*, 234–245.

- [21] Dr. A. Shaji George, & A.S. Hovan George. (2022). Data Sharing Made Easy by Technology Trends: New Data Sharing and Privacy Preserving Technologies that Bring in a New Era of Data Monetization. *Partners Universal International Research Journal (PUIRJ)*, 01(03), 13–19.
- [22] Narver & later. (2016). Competitors Orientation asserted that competitor orientation is one of the dimensions of MO that helps Organization in identifying and analyzing. *Journal of Management and Marketing*, 334–346.
- [23] Never & salter. (2017). customer orientation for the customer continuously, competitor orientation where the seller understands the key strengths, weaknesses, strategies and capabilities of the competition. *International journal of Trade and Tourism*, 123–150.
- [24] Palich & Bagiey. (2015). risk-taking, and personal risk-taking. Entrepreneurs will follow routines or find alternatives to deal with risks. *Journal of business and leadership*, 123=145.
- [25] Sandvik N. (2016). an internal-to-the-Organization readiness to act on market information manifested in well-developed social and cultural inter-functional capabilities. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 123–138.
- [26] Wolff & Petty. (2016). the broader of the managerial orientation-related constructs are insufficiently nuanced tools, particularly in the study of University. . *Journal of Multi disciplinary research Development*, 342–350.